

QUIZ**LAST NAME: SAMSTAD****FIRST NAME: CHRISTINA****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2013 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. The University of New South Wales suggests six steps for essay writing. Which order do they recommend?**
 - Starting the essay, researching the topic, organising your ideas, writing the essay, editing the essay, referencing the essay.
 - Researching the topic, starting the essay, organising your ideas, writing the essay, referencing the essay, editing the essay.
 - Starting the essay, researching the topic, organising your ideas, writing the essay, referencing the essay, editing the essay.¹**
 - Researching the topic, organising your ideas, starting the essay, writing the essay, referencing the essay, editing the essay.
- 2. Which of the following references is an example of citing a book in a bibliography using the Chicago style?**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1-4.

- Wayne C. Booth, Gregory C. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams, *The Craft of Research* (Chicago: University Chicago Press, 1995), 123.
- Booth, Wayne C., Gregory C. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. *The Craft of Research*. Chicago: University Chicago Press, 1995.²**
- Booth, Wayne C., Gregory C. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. 1995. *The Craft of Research*. Chicago: University Chicago Press.
- Booth, W.C., Colomb, G.C., and Williams, J.M. (1995) *The Craft of Research*, Chicago: University Chicago Press.
3. **Being able to produce correct sentences is important for writers. A comma splice, however, is an example of an error that should be avoided. Which of the following sentences gives an example of a comma splice?**
- Reva thought about her favorite school classes, she listed lunch, gym, free time, and art.³**
- When Reva thought about her favorite school classes, she listed lunch, gym, free time, and art.
- Reva thought about her favorite school classes. She listed lunch, gym, free time, and art.
- Reva thought about school and listed lunch, gym, free time, and art as her favorite classes.
4. **Which format do Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer suggest in *Write Source 2000* for entries on a works-cited page (bibliography)?**
- McKissack, Patricia C., and Fredrick McKissack, Jr. *Black Diamond: The Story of the Negro Baseball Leagues*. New York: Scholastic, 1994.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 55.

³ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000. A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning* (Wilmington, Massachusetts: Write Source, 1999), 86.

- McKissack, Patricia C., and Fredrick McKissack, Jr. "Black Diamond: The Story of the Negro Baseball Leagues". New York: Scholastic, 1994.
- McKissack, Patricia C., and Fredrick McKissack, Jr. *Black Diamond: The Story of the Negro Baseball Leagues*. New York: Scholastic, 1994.
- McKissack, Patricia C., and Fredrick McKissack, Jr. Black Diamond: The Story of the Negro Baseball Leagues. New York: Scholastic, 1994.**⁴

5. What are *tertiary sources*?

- Tertiary sources are written for non-specialists. They include encyclopedias and dictionaries, as well as newspapers, magazines, and commercial books written for a general audience.**⁵
- Tertiary sources are books and articles that analyse primary and secondary sources, usually written by and for other researchers.
- Tertiary sources are original works like diaries, letters, manuscripts, images, films, film scripts, recordings, and musical scores created by writers, artists, composers, and so on.
- Tertiary sources are books and articles that analyse secondary sources. They are written for writers, artists, composers, and so on.

6. Which of the following journal paper citations is an example of a Turabian full footnote?

- Bogren, Alexandra. "Gender and Alcohol: The Swedish Press Debate." *Journal of Gender Studies* 20, no. 2 (June 2011): 156.

⁴ Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer, 231.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 8th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory C. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 25.

- Bogren, A. (2011), 'Gender and Alcohol: The Swedish Press Debate', *Journal of Gender Studies*, 20 (2), 156.
- Bogren, Alexandra. 2011. "Gender and Alcohol: The Swedish Press Debate." *Journal of Gender Studies* 20, no. 2 (June): 156.
- Alexandra Bogren, "Gender and Alcohol: The Swedish Press Debate," *Journal of Gender Studies* 20, no. 2 (June 2011): 156.⁶**

7. Which type of highlighting does the *University of Oxford Style Guide* recommend for embedding foreign words in an English text?

- Quotation marks
- Italics⁷**
- Underlining
- Bold

8. Which format does the *Harvard Citing and Referencing Guide* recommend for online journal articles?

- Hogan, Jenny. "Snapshot, face facts: a blow for Mars conspiracy theorists." *Nature* 443, (September 28, 2006): 379 Accessed January 24, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.1038/443379a> (January 24, 2010).
- Hogan, Jenny. 2006. "Snapshot, face facts: a blow for Mars conspiracy theorists." *Nature* 443, (September 28): 379 Accessed January 24, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.1038/443379a>
- Hogan, J. (2006) 'Snapshot, face facts: a blow for Mars conspiracy theorists', *Nature*, 443, 28 September, 379, available:**

⁶ Turabian, 92.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 94.

<http://www.nature.com/nature/journal/v443/n7110/full/443379a.html> [accessed 24 January 2010].⁸

- Hogan, J. "Snapshot, face facts: a blow for Mars conspiracy theorists." *Nature* 443. 28 Sept. 2006, 379. 24 Jan. 2010 <<http://www.nature.com/nature/journal/v443/n7110/full/443379a.html>>.

9. **The *WHO Style Guide* lists three advantages of a house style. Which of the following answers is not one of them?**

- House style ensures consistency.
- House style contributes to a corporate image of "one WHO".
- House style ensures your article will be published.**⁹
- House style streamlines and increases the efficiency of writing and editing.

10. **Which format do WHO publications base their reference list on?**

- A reference list in a WHO publication is based on the so-called Chicago style.
- A reference list in a WHO publication is based on the so-called Harvard style.
- A reference list in a WHO publication is based on the so-called Turabian style.
- A reference list in a WHO publication is based on the so-called Vancouver style.**¹⁰

⁸ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 64.

⁹ WHO, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 1.

¹⁰ WHO, 25.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000. A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*. Wilmington, Massachusetts: Write Source, 1999.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 8th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory C. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.

WHO. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.